

HOW TO BECOME A LAWYER IN CHINA

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Abstract: This article will explore the conditions and procedures for becoming a lawyer in China based on the Lawyers Law of the People's Republic of China and the Implementation Measures for the National Unified Legal Professional Qualification Examination.

Keywords: Chinese lawyers, conditions for becoming a lawyer, lawyers

China's legal profession has gone through decades of development, from its initial establishment to its recovery and development. Each stage reflects the process of the country's rule of law construction and the context of social development. With the deepening of China's reform and opening up and the construction of the rule of law, the role of lawyers in the judicial system has become increasingly prominent, becoming one of the important forces in promoting the rule of law and maintaining fairness and justice. However, becoming a lawyer is not easy. It requires rigorous qualification examinations, professional internship training, and good moral character. This article will explore the conditions and procedures for becoming a lawyer in contemporary China, as well as the legal system and social background behind it.

Since the founding of the People's Republic of China, China's legal profession has gone through more than 60 years of development, during which it has gone through stages such as initial establishment, cancellation, reconstruction, and resumption of development.

Current Chinese lawyer system was restored and established based on the Criminal Procedure Law of the People's Republic of China in 1979 and the Interim Regulations on Lawyers of the People's Republic of China in 1980. Affected by various factors, for a long time the number of judges and prosecutors far exceeded the number of lawyers.

After more than 30 years of reform and development, the above situation has undergone significant structural changes. By the end of 2017, the number of lawyers in China had exceeded 365,000, becoming an important force in promoting economic and social development and building a country ruled by law.

So how can one become a lawyer in China today?

According to Article 5 of the Lawyers Law of the People's Republic of China, to apply for practicing as a lawyer, one must meet the following conditions:

- 1) To uphold the Constitution of the People's Republic of China;
- 2) Having passed the National Unified Judicial Examination;
- 3) Having interned in a law firm for one year;
- 4) Good moral character.

Among them, the second and third are the key elements to becoming a lawyer in China.

In summary, in China, one must first sign up for the National Unified Legal Professional Qualification Examination. After passing the examination, one must intern in a law firm for one year before one can apply to practice as a lawyer.

So what are the requirements for taking the National Unified Legal Profession Qualification Examination ? The regulations are in the "Implementation Measures for the National Unified Legal Profession Qualification Examination" .

Article 9 specifies in detail the conditions for applying for the National Unified Legal Professional Qualification Examination.

Persons who meet the following conditions may apply for the National Unified Legal Professional Qualification Examination:

- 1) Having the nationality of the People's Republic of China;
- 2) To uphold the Constitution of the People's Republic of China and enjoy the right to vote and to be elected;
- 3) Having good political, professional qualities and moral character;
- 4) Having full capacity for civil conduct;
- 5) Possess a bachelor's degree in law from a full-time regular college and obtain a bachelor's degree or above; possess a bachelor's degree or above in non-law subjects from a full-time regular college and obtain a master's degree in law, master of jurisprudence or above; possess a bachelor's degree or above in non-law subjects from a full-time regular college and obtain a corresponding degree and have been engaged in legal work for at least three years.

Article 10 also specifies in detail the conditions that cannot include the National Unified Legal Professional Qualification Examination.

Persons who meet any of the following conditions shall not register for the National Unified Legal Professional Qualification Examination:

- 1) Having been punished for an intentional crime;

2) Those who have been dismissed from public office or have had their lawyer's practice certificate or notary public's practice certificate revoked;

3) Having his/her legal professional qualification certificate revoked;

4) The period of being prohibited from registering for the National Unified Legal Professional Qualification Examination (National Judicial Examination) for two years has not expired, or the person has been prohibited from registering for the National Unified Legal Professional Qualification Examination (National Judicial Examination) for life;

5) Those who have been identified as targets of joint punishment for dishonesty by relevant state agencies due to serious dishonesty and included in the national credit information sharing platform;

6) Those who have been banned from engaging in legal profession for life due to other circumstances.

If a person is in any of the circumstances specified in the preceding paragraph, his registration will be invalid if he has already completed the registration procedures; if he has already taken the examination, his examination results will be invalid.

Therefore, we can conclude that in today's China, only citizens of the People's Republic of China who have obtained a bachelor's degree in law or above, have good conduct, no criminal record, and have passed the National Unified Legal Professional Qualification Examination can become lawyers after one year of internship in a law firm.

From this we can see that becoming a lawyer in China is not an easy thing. The procedure is complicated and the requirements are high. Generally, only high-quality legal talents who have undergone a lot of professional training can become lawyers in China.

The development of China's legal profession not only bears witness to the process of China's rule of law construction, but also reflects the society's unremitting pursuit of fairness and justice. Becoming a lawyer is a career that requires profound legal knowledge, good moral qualities and persistent efforts. Driven by China's rule of law process, lawyers will continue to play an important role in promoting social fairness and justice and safeguarding legal rights.

References:

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